

Article

Artificial Intelligence Influencers' Credibility Effect on Consumer Engagement and Purchase Intention

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Abstract: In the evolving world of influencer marketing, Artificial Intelligence (AI) influencers are creating significant impact and transforming the approach to brand promotions on social media platforms. In recent times, many popular brands have partnered with AI influencers to engage with their social media audiences. AI influencers have become popular as a novel method for brands to increase customer engagement and create purchase intention, but there is a scarcity of research on this emerging trend of marketing. The AI-based virtual influencers effect on consumer engagement and purchase intention remain largely unexplored. This study used a questionnaire-based survey method and 414 responses were collected. The result from the research shows that credibility, informative value and human-likeness are the major factors influencing consumer engagement purchase intention towards brands promoted through AI-based virtual influencers. The attractiveness and entertainment value of AI influencer's social media posts affect consumer engagement but exhibit no effect on purchase intention. Theoretical and managerial recommendations related to AI influencers' marketing are presented.

Keywords: influencer marketing; artificial intelligence (AI); social media; virtual influencer; AI influencer; consumer engagement; purchase intention; credibility; informative value; entertainment value; human-likeness; attractiveness

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1. Introduction

Social media influencers perform the role of digital opinion leaders by sharing online videos of their personal lives, opinions, and experiences, which attracts many followers. They also collaborate with brands to present sponsored content about the brand. In recent times, social media influencers have been found to be increasingly popular in attracting huge followers and to have the ability to influence the audience's attitudes, preferences and buying decisions [1,2]. Influencer marketing is the approach of using social media influencers to promote a brand which is constantly evolving and poised for significant growth due to increased adoptions by marketers and consumers. One of the emerging categories of social media influencers is the non-human artificial intelligence (AI) influencer or virtual influencers (VI), which are computer-generated personalities that look like humans and mimic human behavior. AI influencers are virtual personas developed using artificial intelligence technology and have the ability to interact with consumers via social media platforms. Global influencer marketing was valued around USD 24 billion in 2024 [3]; the virtual influencer market was USD 4.6 billion in 2024 and it is estimated to increase by 38.9% to USD 8.3 billion by 2025 [4]. AI-based non-human influencers have generated

substantial followers and are increasingly being used by brands for their social media promotions. The emergence of AI influencers raises several questions about the effect on engagement and behavioral intentions towards the brand. AI influencers provide content control, an absence of scandals and innovative storytelling, but their main disadvantages are the high cost of developing, a lack of credibility and the challenge of executing new marketing campaigns. Therefore, understanding the impact and consumers’ responses to these new AI influencers is an important issue for marketers and for academic researchers.

Artificial Intelligence is widely referred as a system that exhibits intelligent behavior by assessing the environment and performing appropriate actions [5]. AI-based influencers can be developed by adopting various technologies like machine learning, deep learning, physical robots, natural language processing, rule-based expert systems and neural networks [6]. The AI algorithms are able to create realistic facial expressions, body movements and voices that make the model look like a human. Examples of AI-powered technologies include robots, avatars, virtual bots and touchscreen kiosks [7]. An AI-based virtual influencer avatar, or fictional character, is one of the AI-based products which are gaining popularity in social media. The significant growth of artificial intelligence (AI), social media and the metaverse has enabled marketers to create and use AI-based virtual influencers (VI) for various brand promotions [8]. These AI influencers are used by leading brands like Channel, Red Bull, Calvin Klein and Prada to promote their brands. Table 1 lists the popular AI influencers and their number of followers.

Table 1. AI influencers on Instagram and their profiles (as of June 2024).

Virtual Influencer	Country	Followers	Posts	Profile	Brand Collaborations
Lu do Magalu	Brazil	6,900,000	2378	Unboxing videos and product reviews	Red Bull, McDonalds and Adidas
Lil Miquela	USA	2,100,000	1323	Musician and Style Visionary	Calvin Klein, Prada, BMW
Aitana Lopez	Spain	312,000	110	Fitness lover	Olaplex, Brandy Melville Spain and Intimissimi
Kyra	India	273,000	92	Model and Traveler	BoAt, Realme and Titian Eyecare
Naina AVT	India	212,000	355	Fashion, Beauty, Fitness and Entertainment	Fikaa

The shift from human to AI influencers on social media represents a notable change. Artificial Intelligence influencers are based on AI technologies but are designed and controlled by a team of creative people, while human influencers depend completely on the human experience and personal narratives [9]. One of the main challenges of AI influencers is the lack of genuine emotions and authenticity [10]. This may undermine the credibility perception towards AI influencers. This will affect the followers’ engagement and purchase intentions. Previous research has shown that consumers follow AI influencers just as much as they do human influencers [11]. AI influencers show positive brand attitudes, word-of-mouth and higher purchase intentions similar to human influencers [12]. AI-based virtual influencers show some advantages over human influencers in terms of availability, ease of control and reduced risks of negative PR and scandals [13]. AI influencers excel in engaging, creative and visually stunning brand presentations. Table 2 highlights the uniqueness of AI influencers as compared to human influencers. Some brands favor non-human influencers instead of human influencers for their brand promotions for a variety of reasons like novelty in storytelling, better control of the appearance of the virtual influencer and cost savings [14,15].

In spite of all the differences, research by HypeAuditor shows that virtual influencers show higher engagement rates and growth retention than traditional human influencers [16,17]. Furthermore, an AI influencer's age is not changed unless creators change it and can be used to develop innovative campaigns. This innovative new communication strategy reduces follower fatigue among younger consumers compared to human influencers [18]. The cost of AI influencers is less than that of human influencers [16]. These AI influencers built by AI algorithms reduce the difference between reality and the digital world, however, their impactful presence will be based on the authenticity of the content produced by AI influencers. Beyond their beautiful appearance created by cutting-edge technologies like deep learning, computer vision, machine learning and natural language processing, their digital personas play an important role as influential tools in marketing.

Understanding these non-human influencers is crucial for grasping the evolving dynamics of consumer engagement and influencers' marketing [19]. The current research is based on human-like models named as AI influencers, which are also powered by AI technologies. The AI influencers' related research has been growing in popularity and importance in recent times but it is still in its infancy stage [1]. A significant number of researchers have studied the human social media influencers and their effect on attitude, intention and actual behavior in the last few years [20], but limited studies have been conducted on non-human AI influencers or virtual influencers [21–24]. There is only a limited amount of studies that have exclusively examined AI influencers, as most of the previous research has focused more broadly on virtual influencers [8]. Few research studies on AI influencers have focused on comparing the effects of human and virtual influencers (e.g., Böhndel et al.) [23].

Table 2. Characteristics of human influencers and AI influencers.

Characteristics	Human Influencers	AI Influencers
Origin	Real human	Artificially created persona created by advanced algorithms, machine learning and AI technologies.
Appearance	Limited by the characteristics of each person	Unlimited options available to create characteristics according to the brand requirements.
Emotions	Exhibits person's emotions and can be driven by positive or negative emotional behaviors [21].	They lack their own emotions, and their behavior is more stable and is not guided by positive or negative emotions.
Credibility	This is conditioned by their degree of knowledge and by the independence of their opinions [21].	Interactions appear genuine as they can be personalized, and they are conditioned by the degree of information processing and elaboration associated with AI technologies.
Efficiency	Its efficiency is based on the influencer	Efficiency is based on the information processing program

The effectiveness of social media human influencers has been proven by researchers, but AI Influencers' effectiveness still remains limited [25]. Previous research on AI influencers mostly focused on human-like character and its impact, and the results are inconsistent [1]. Few previous studies have shown that human-like VIs are less effective than non-human-like VIs [26], but some studies show that more human-like VIs are trustworthy and elicit favorable reactions from the users [27]. There are only limited articles that

have focused exclusively on AI influencers, as much of the previous research has studied virtual influencers only generally [8]. The AI influencers' visual appearance and interactive ability is widely acknowledged for its influence on creating better user experiences and behavioral intention [28]. There is considerable improvement in AI influencers' visual appearances due to the usage of AI technologies. Most of the early studies conducted on non-human influencers was related to animated virtual influencers and very few studies have been conducted using human-like virtual influencers. Limited knowledge is available to researchers and practitioners about followers' characteristics and the factors that drive them to interact with AI influencers in the social media environment.

Youn et al. identified three perspectives of research on VIs, namely, behavioral, cognitive and affective [28]. Behavioral research focuses mainly on consumer engagement, engagement rate, word of mouth, and purchase rate [28,29]. The cognitive perspective focuses on source credibility, trustworthiness, attractiveness and information quality like usefulness. The third category of the research focuses on the emotional aspect of VIs [28]. Although consumer engagement on social media is widely studied, there is limited understanding of consumer engagement with AI Influencers' social media pages. The current research is based on human-like models named as AI influencers, which are also powered by AI technologies. This research focuses on identifying the factors that influence consumers' engagement and purchase intentions towards the AI influencers' post in social media. The previous research shows that credibility attracts the audience specifically due to expertise and trustworthiness [29]. Few research findings show that AI-based, non-human influencers appear less trustworthy, which leads to less engagement [11]. But few researchers' findings show that uniqueness and expertise lead to higher engagement [21]. Literature reviews related to the effect of influencers on consumer engagement are scarce as the field is still developing, and most of the studies have focused on purchase intention [30]. This research's main objective is to investigate and establish the relationship between AI influencers and consumers' buying behavior in relation to them. This research contributes to the influencer marketing literature by identifying the factors that influence engagement and intention through analysis and modeling.

2. Literature Review

Artificial intelligence influencers are computer-generated personas with a human-like appearance and perform similar tasks to those of human influencers [11]. AI influencers are a new and evolving phenomenon that was recently coined in the academic literature [1]. In early studies, the term "virtual influencers" was widely used by researchers, and these can be classified as computer-generated imagery (CGI) and AI influencers [11,12]. AI influencers create content and interact with consumers using artificial intelligence technologies. Virtual influencers based on appearance can be categorized into three types, namely, anime VIs, human-like VIs and non-human-like VIs (toys and animals) [1]. The current research focuses on the behavior and cognitive perspective of AI influencers. The usage of AI influences on social media is a recent trend, and a few research studies on AI influencers are presented in Table 3. The research shows that a significant number of studies were conducted to understand the influencers and their effect on intention and actual behavior. But the research on AI-based virtual influencers is in its early stage, though growing. Some of the important theories and models which were applied to study the AI influencers' effectiveness are Uncanny Valley Theory and Anthropomorphism Theory [31,32], the Advertising Value Model [33], the Source Credibility Theory [34], the Uses and Gratifications Theory (UGT) [35], and the Computer as Social Actors Paradigm (CASA) [36].

A good amount of research on virtual influencers has been conducted to study the uncanny valley and anthropomorphism phenomenon. The previous research findings

show mixed results. Pan, Qin and Zhang applied the uncanny valley phenomenon to investigate the effects of the level of anthropomorphizing of virtual influencers on livestreaming e-commerce platforms [37]. Their research findings show that virtual influencers with a medium-realistic image reduce purchase intentions compared to cartoon images. Belanche et al. conducted experiments to study the intention to adopt virtual and human influencers [21]. In recent years, a number of researchers have applied U and G theory to explain the motivating factor for consuming social media. Based on the previous research using U and G theory, information value and entertainment value are considered the important factors for social media usage. Other important factors for accepting AI influencers are the informative and entertainment values, which are based on UGT. The research findings of Lou, Kiew, Chen, Lee, Ong and Phua show that users want to follow VI due to its entertainment and informative content [38].

According to the source credibility theory [34], the influencers’ expertise, trustworthiness and attractiveness can positively affect attitude and behavior. Previous studies on human influencers on social media predominantly applied source credibility theory, and it was found to be one of the important factors for increasing the purchase intention, but limited studies have been conducted to study the effect of AI influencers’ credibility on engagement and purchase intention. The research of Agnihotri, Chaturvedi and Tripathi on virtual influencer followers on Instagram shows that credibility significantly affects followers’ buying behavior [39]. U and G theory [35] contributes to explaining the reasons for users to consume a particular media type and content. They found that virtual influencers’ positive comments about a product or service were found to be more useful for utilitarian products. Recent research on virtual influencers shows that they significantly influence consumer purchase decisions [40]. Due to the infancy of AI-based virtual influencers in marketing, the intention to follow remains limited and requires detailed exploration.

Table 3. Recent studies on AI influencers.

Authors/Year	Country	Antecedents	Consequences
Alboqami (2023) [41]	Saudi Arabia	Attractiveness, Credibility and Congruences	Trust
Gerlich (2023) [42]	Switzerland	Trust, Credibility and Expertise	Purchase Intention
Wang, Xue, Liu and Loi (2024) [43]	China	Social Media Presence, Fantasy and Attitude towards endorser	Purchase Intention
Feng, Chen and Xie (2024) [44]	United States	Anthropomorphism, Artificiality, Attractiveness, Luminary, Quality, Trendiness and Robophobia	Consumers’ Acceptance, Trust, Attitude
Kong and Fang (2024) [45]	China	Attractiveness, Expertise and Trustworthiness	Product attitude

2.1. Informative Value and Entertainment Value of AI Influencers

Ducoffee (1995)’s advertising value model defines advertising value as the total value consumers receive by watching advertisements [33]. The model suggests that the value of advertising is derived from two primary components: informative value and entertainment value. This means that effective advertising should both provide useful information to

the audience and entertain them to capture and maintain their attention [33]. Uses and gratifications theory explains the motivation to use different media to satisfy their social and psychological needs [35]. Influencer marketing can also be considered as a form of non-paid advertising as the post content is informative and entertaining to the consumers [46]. Previous studies on social media influencers shows that informative value affects purchase intention [29,46]. Engaging social media posts that entertain can motivate consumer interest to follow and lead to higher purchase intentions [38].

2.2. Attractionness and Human-Likeness of AI Influencers

Previous research indicates that consumers are more likely to form connections with virtual influencers if these influencers exhibit more human-like characteristics [47]. Feng, Chen and Quan Zie's research identified six key attributes, which are "anthropomorphism, attractiveness, luminary, quality, trendiness and robophobia" [44]. Looi and Kahlor studied Instagram posts of 424 human and virtual influencers, and found that both types of influencers predominantly conveyed positive sentiments [48]. Shen studied 33 virtual influencers on Instagram, and the research findings reveal that non-sponsored posts by the virtual influencers exhibit higher engagement than sponsored posts [24]. The computers are social actors (CASA) paradigm states that computers exhibit similar social attributes to humans so the human's computer interactions are similar to human interactions [36]. Researchers have applied this theoretical framework to various human computer interactions from desktop computers to AI technologies like human–chatbot interactions, voice assistants and social robots [49]. Previous studies indicate that human influencers generate higher engagement than virtual influencers [48]. Additionally, Böhdnel et al.'s research reveals that customer–brand engagement is not influenced by the perceived authenticity and humanization of virtual influencers [23].

2.3. Credibility of AI Influencers

The source credibility model has been widely utilized in research on influencer marketing [50]. Source credibility theory proposed by Hovland and Weiss (1952) postulates that the credibility of the endorsers could influence the beliefs, attitudes and behaviors of receivers [34]. Credibility is a multidimensional construct which consists of three primary factors: expertise, trustworthiness and goodwill [51]. The studies conducted by Gerlich in Switzerland show that consumers are becoming more attracted to virtual influencers, viewing them as more trustworthy, credible and aligned with their preferences, which subsequently enhances their intention to make purchases [42]. Agnihotri, Chaturvedi and Tripathi [39] studied 538 followers of Instagram virtual influencers, and their finding shows that credibility significantly affects engagement and purchase intention.

2.4. Consumer Engagement and Purchase Intention of AI Influencers

Consumer engagement is one of the primary metrics for measuring the success of social media marketing campaigns [52]. Consumer engagement can be defined as the level of interaction between the consumer and users of social media through views, likes, comments, shares, posts, etc. Participation in social media can be classified into passive and active participation—passive involves, for example, viewing posts, and active participation involves, for example, liking, sharing, or commenting on social media posts [6]. Researchers consider engagement as a multi-dimensional concept that comprises cognitive, emotional and behavioral aspects [53]. Influencer characteristics and the content of the post are two important factors that drive user engagement with social media influencers [1]. In the context of social media, consumer engagement can be in the form of viewing the content, liking the content, and sharing and making comments on their post. Many researchers have attempted to identify factors that increase social media engagement with influencers'

posts. Previous studies have shown that virtual influencers’ posts on Instagram tend to receive more likes and positive emojis than human influencers’ ones [16].

Customer social media engagement has been recognized as a crucial element in predicting and understanding consumer behavior outcomes, including purchase intention [53]. Established technology acceptance theories like reasoned action theory, the technology acceptance model and the planned behavior theory treat intention as a predictor for actual user behavior. Engaged consumers on social media brand pages usually exhibit a positive attitude towards the brand and also show higher intention to buy [54]. Consequently, we will also utilize purchase intention as our outcome variable to examine how customer engagement influences viewers’ intention to make a purchase.

3. Conceptual Framework and Hypothesis Development

3.1. Factors Affecting AI Influencers’ Page Engagement and Purchase Intention

Previous research shows that consumer engagement on social media brand pages affect behavioral intention [25]. More recently, researchers have started to study AI-based virtual influencers and their applications in marketing. Influencers’ marketing researchers applied multiple theories, including the theory of reasoned action, social exchange theory, credibility theory, interactivity theory, theory of planned behavior and social comparison theory. Based on the literature review, the main factors influencing the engagement and purchase intention towards AI influencers are informative value, exertainment value, attractiveness, human-likeness and credibility. Conceptual Framework of the Study is presented in Figure 1. The following section presents a detailed overview of the above-mentioned factors.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework of the Study.

3.2. Informative Value

Information provided by the social media influencers is one of the important factors that motivate consumers to view, follow and participate in the brand’s social media

pages [55]. AI influencers' content informative value can be described as the posts that provide information about products or services which help the consumers to purchase [46]. Consumers regard influencers' posts as informative as they give details about the product quality, features, user experiences and offers [56]. The informative value of the post is based on the usefulness to consumers. The informativeness of social media posts positively affects the behavioral responses [57]. Previous research has shown that social media influencers' post content informative value has a positive effect on consumer engagement and purchase intention [46]. Chen and Lou's research findings show that influencers' posts' informative value positively affects followers' purchase intentions [29]. This suggests that consumer engagement mediates the informative value on purchase intention.

H₁: *Informative value has a positive effect on consumer engagement on AI influencers' social media pages.*

H₂: *Informative value has a positive effect on purchase intention.*

3.3. Entertainment Value

Entertainment value can be defined as the AI influencers' posts which can entertain consumers. Influencers' posts can entertain and potentially influence followers' thoughts, attitudes and behaviors [46]. Chen and Lin [58] state that entertainment involves emotional elements like fun, enjoyment and pleasure, which significantly influence followers' likelihood of forming a stronger attachment to the influencer. Previous research shows that the entertainment value of the influencers' posts impacts the engagement and purchase intentions [56,59].

H₃: *Entertainment value has a positive effect on consumer engagement on AI influencers' social media pages.*

H₄: *Entertainment value has a positive effect on purchase intention.*

3.4. Attractiveness

Attractiveness refers to the degree to which the endorser is pleasant and is crucial in the online socialization process [60]. The source attractiveness model explains that the celebrity's familiarity, likeability and appearance during an advertisement have a certain degree of effect on the respondents' behavior [61]. Kim and Park's research reveals that virtual influencers' attractiveness does not directly affect the purchase intention but provides favorable perceptions. This study focuses on the AI influencer's attractiveness and analyzes how it affects consumer engagement and purchase intention. Previous studies on virtual influencers' attractiveness show that it influences both engagement and purchase intention [62].

H₅: *Attractiveness has a positive effect on consumer engagement on AI influencers' social media pages.*

H₆: *Attractiveness has a positive effect on purchase intention.*

3.5. Human-Likeness

The importance of anthropomorphism or human-likeness is considered one of the important attributes for the acceptance of AI influencers by consumers. The computers are social actor theory (CASA) [36] paradigm explains that computers are treated as social actors and people like to interact. Ma and Li [63]'s research on virtual influencers and brand engagement shows that a human-like appearance results in higher purchase intentions. A survey by Dabiran, Farivar and Wang reveals that human-likeness has a positive

effect on purchase intentions [64]. The acceptance of human-like AI influencers is the existence of human-like physical characteristics, and behavioral and/or emotional intelligence. Rahman et al.'s (2023) research shows that non-human digital communications simulate a more realistic experience and result in enhanced customer engagement [65]. Kim's research findings shows that human-like virtual influencers have higher content engagement and purchase intent than anime-like virtual influencers [66]. Based on these studies, we pose the following hypothesis:

H₇: *Human-likeness has a positive effect on consumer engagement with AI influencers' social media pages.*

H₈: *Human-likeness has a positive effect on purchase intention.*

3.6. Credibility

The source credibility model has been used widely in studies of influencer marketing [50]. The credibility of the communicator is an important factor which can change the opinion of the receiver [34]. The research shows that credibility attracts the audience specifically due to expertise and trustworthiness [29]. The perceived credibility of endorsers has been demonstrated to be a precursor to their followers' behavioral intentions to keep up with their updates and act on the information shared in their blogs. [67]. The previous research shows that customers intend to follow the advice of an influencer with a high credibility rating [56]. Social media influencers are used by brands due to their credibility and expertise [68]. Agnihotri, Chaturvedi and Tripathi [39]'s research on Instagram virtual influencers reveals that credibility significantly affects purchase intentions, except in the trustworthiness dimension, but it substantially mediates virtual engagement.

H₉: *Credibility has a positive effect on consumer engagement on AI influencers' social media page.*

H₁₀: *Credibility has a positive effect on purchase intention.*

3.7. Consumer Engagement and Purchase Intention

In this study, purchase intention is defined as the probability or likelihood of a consumer making a purchase [42]. Many researchers have used purchase intentions to evaluate the effectiveness of marketing strategies. Many researchers are able to prove that consumer engagement leads to higher purchase intention [69,70]. Lou et al. (2023) found that virtual influencers can effectively build brand awareness and a positive image, but they fall short of persuading consumers to make purchases due to their lack of authenticity [38]. Social media marketing has been found to have a positive effect on purchase intention, which is mediated by consumer brand engagement [71].

H₁₁: *Consumer engagement has a positive effect on purchase intention.*

3.8. Mediating Effect of Consumer Engagement on Relationship Between Informative Value, Entertainment Value, Attractiveness, Human-Likeness and Credibility on Purchase Intention

This study examines the direct and indirect effects of informative value, entertainment value, attractiveness, human-likeness and credibility on consumer engagement and purchase intention towards AI influencers' posts. In this study, consumer engagement is measured as consuming, contributing and creating content on AI influencers' social media pages. Previous research findings indicate that relevant, engaging and valuable content can increase consumer engagement, strengthening the intention to purchase. Yang and Lin's research on augmented reality (AR) retail shows that media usefulness and media enjoyment directly affect purchase intention, which is partially mediated by consumer

engagement [72]. Sardar, Tata and Sarkar's research on fashion influencers reveals that consumer engagement mediates between source credibility and purchase intention. Not many studies conducted mediate the effect on consumer engagement [73]. Thus, we propose the following hypotheses:

H_{11a}: *Customer engagement fully mediates the relationship between informative value and purchase intention.*

H_{11b}: *Customer engagement fully mediates the relationship between entertainment value and purchase intention.*

H_{11c}: *Customer engagement fully mediates the relationship between attractiveness and purchase intention.*

H_{11d}: *Customer engagement fully mediates the relationship between human-likeness and purchase intention.*

H_{11e}: *Customer engagement fully mediates the relationship between credibility and purchase intention.*

4. Methodology

4.1. Data Collection

The study adopted a quantitative research method to investigate the factors that affect consumer engagement on an AI influencer's page and the motivation of a consumer to make a purchase. To study the impact of an artificial intelligence influencer on consumer engagement and the intention to purchase, an online survey questionnaire was used. Written informed consent was obtained from the participants before they answered the questionnaire. The survey forms were distributed via Google Forms and SurveyMonkey. To reduce common method bias, participants needed to answer questions based on their self-reports. However, to enhance response accuracy, it was important to provide participants with information and instructions before the research. The introduction part of the questionnaire provided a link to an Indian AI influencer (Nina)'s video for the respondents to learn about AI influencers. An online questionnaire was circulated via social media pages and emails. The data were collected from April 2024 to June 2024. For participant selection, a convenience sampling was applied, choosing those who were willing to participate in the research.

The target audience of this study are users in the age group between 18 and 37, as previous research shows that 75 percent of this age group follow AI-based virtual influencers [74]. This study focuses on AI influencers on Instagram as the survey on influencer marketing shows that Instagram was the most preferred platform for the influencers marketing in India [75]. A total of 86 percent of the respondents in this study were between the ages of 18 and 27 years old. Schreiber et al. recommended that the N:q ratio should be 10 to 1, or 10 observations (participants) for each estimated parameter in the model [76]. The present study's sample size was 414, which fulfills the 10 to 1 rule of sample size. The online survey received 420 complete responses, which were used for analysis, six incomplete responses set were removed from the analysis, resulting in 414 as the final sample size.

4.2. Variables and Measurement Items

There are seven variables in the proposed model to understand the impact of AI influencers: (1) informative value, (2) entertainment value, (3) attractiveness, (4) human-likeness, (5) credibility, (6) consumer engagement, and (7) purchase intention. Based on the above-mentioned variables, a questionnaire was developed to investigate the effect of

the adapted variables on purchase intention. Consumer engagement was measured using the COBRA framework [77]. This framework categorizes social media engagement into three types. They are consuming, contributing and creating. The consuming COBRA type represents a minimum level of online brand-related activeness, and creating a COBRA type represents the ultimate level of online brand-related activeness [65]. Based on this, we have included three items in the questionnaire covering all the three levels of engagement.

The measurement items used in this study were adapted from earlier works of the authors and modified for the context related to AI influencers. This survey questionnaire has a total of 36 questions, and 26 questions were constructed using a Likert scale with points ranging from 1 to 5. The 26-item scale questions used a five-point Likert scale which consisted of Strongly Disagree = 1 and Strongly Agree = 5 measures. The variables were shortlisted after a detailed literature review. The credibility of AI influencers was measured using three items from Magano, Au-Yong-Oliveira, Walter and Leite [78]. The sources of other constructs were operationalized and presented in Table 4. The introduction part of the questionnaire provides the link to an AI influencer (NAINA)’s Instagram page “https://www.instagram.com/naina_avtr/?hl=en (accessed on 15 September 2024)” for the respondents to learn about AI influencers. This study focuses on AI influencers on Instagram as the survey on influencer marketing shows that Instagram was the most preferred platform for the influencers marketing in India [75]. The latent variables were adapted from the previous literature with adequate reliability.

Table 4. Scale items and its source.

Construct	Scale Items	Source(s)
Information Value (INF)	The information shared by the AI influencer is useful.	[79]
	The information shared by the AI influencer is helpful to find product information.	[80]
	The information shared by the AI influencer is important for selecting the product.	[80]
Entertainment Value (ENT)	The AI influencer posts are entertaining.	[79]
	Watching AI influencer posts are fun.	[79]
	Watching AI influencer posts are thrilling.	[80]
Attractiveness (ATT)	The AI influencer is attractive.	[78]
	The AI influencer is charismatic.	[78]
	The AI influencer is good-looking.	[78]
Human-likeness (HL)	The AI influencer looks like a human.	[81]
	The AI influencer is life-like.	[81]
	The AI influencer gets involved in human-centric communication.	[82]
	The AI influencer has human-like expressions.	[82]
Credibility (CRE)	The AI influencer(s) is/are trustworthy.	[78]
	The AI influencer(s) is/are reliable.	[78]
	The virtual influencers are experts in their field.	[78]
Customer Engagement (CE)	I watch the picture/photos and videos posted on the virtual influencer’s social media page.	[77,79]
	I like the content posted on the virtual influencer’s social media page.	[77,79]
	I follow the virtual influencer’s social media page.	[77,79]

Table 4. *Cont.*

Construct	Scale Items	Source(s)
Purchase Intention (PI)	I will buy products promoted by the AI influencer in the near future.	[83]
	I intend to purchase the products promoted by the AI influencers in the near future.	[83]
	It is likely that I will purchase the products promoted by the AI influencers in the near future.	[83]
	I expect to purchase the products promoted by the AI influencers in the near future.	[83]

5. Data Analysis

To study the impact of artificial intelligence's influence on consumer engagement and the intention to purchase, an online survey questionnaire was used. The survey was distributed via Google Forms and SurveyMonkey. The target audience of this study are Gen Z users, as previous research shows that 75 percent of Gen Z are following AI-based virtual influencers [74]. The collected data were analyzed using SPSS and AMOS version 29.

5.1. Respondents Characteristics

A total of 414 respondents answered the online survey questionnaire. A total of 51.7% of the respondents were male and 48.3 were female. The majority of the respondents were university students, and all the respondents used Instagram. A total of 43.5 percent of the respondents were working. The age group between 18 and 22 years old accounted for 41.8 of the sample, and the age group between 23 and 27 years old accounted for 44.4% of the sample. The details of the respondents' profile are presented in Table 5. Social media usage amongst our participants was as follows: 80 percent of the respondents primarily follow influencers on Instagram, which is followed by YouTube and Facebook. Only 20% of the respondents currently followed AI influencers.

Table 5. Respondents' characteristics.

	Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	214	51.7
	Female	200	48.3
Age	18–22	173	41.8
	23–27	184	44.4
	28–32	35	8.5
	33–37	22	5.3
Education	Graduate	258	62.3
	Postgraduate	156	37.7
Income	Less than INR 30,000	228	55.1
	INR 30,001–INR 60,000	113	27.3
	INR 60,001–INR 90,000	46	11.1
	INR 90,001–INR 120,000	16	3.9
	Above INR 120,001	11	2.7

Table 5. *Cont.*

	Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage
Occupation	Student	225	54.4
	Working	157	37.9
	Entrepreneur	23	5.6
	Unemployed	9	2.1

The descriptive analysis of the respondents also reveals that 32.12 percent of the respondents are following virtual or human influencers' social media pages. The survey data also show that 34.4 percent of respondents strongly trust human social media influencers. The AI influencer's social media page consumer engagement and purchase intention were found to be higher for respondents who followed human influencers and showed higher trust towards them. This shows that respondents who responded to human influencers were more likely to respond to virtual influencers.

5.2. Common-Method Bias Test

The data for this research were derived from the self-reported questionnaire, and it was necessary to check for common methodological biases as it is prone to common method bias. Harman's single-factor test was used for the common method bias. The total variance extracted by one factor was 38.494, which was below the recommended threshold of 50% [84]. Also, the survey was anonymous, which eliminated the possibility of the social desirability effect on respondents' answers [85].

5.3. Measurement Validity

The first step of the structural equation model (SEM) analysis is to analyze the outer model (measurement model). The purpose of this analysis is to determine how well the scale item loads on the construct [86]. The evaluation of the reflective outer model includes examining the reliability of individual items (indicator reliability), the reliability of each latent variable, internal consistency (using Cronbach's alpha and composite reliability), construct validity (loading and cross-loading), convergent validity (average variance extracted, AVE) and discriminant validity (using the Fornell–Larcker criterion, cross-loading and the HTMT criterion) [87]. The benchmark of construct validity assessments is that the factor loadings must be more than or equal to 0.70, and the CR of each construct must be equal to 0.70 or above [87–89]. The KMO Bartlett's test was conducted to assess sampling adequacy. The KMO value was 0.920, which is considered excellent as it surpassed the 0.5 threshold. The KMO value was 0.920, which is considered excellent value as it exceeded the threshold of 0.5 [87].

The initial analysis indicated that one item from the human-likeness needed to be dropped due to having a loading below 0.50. To check the internal consistency reliability of the measure, composite reliability and Cronbach's alpha values were analyzed [87]. According to Hair et al. the composite reliability and Cronbach's alpha values for all measured constructs need to exceed 0.7 and AVE should be greater than 0.5 [87]. The reliability for each construct was measured using Cronbach's alpha, which ranged from 0.794 to 0.869, all above the minimum standard of 0.7, indicating high reliability. To check the convergent validity of the measurement model, the average extracted variance (AVE) values were assessed and presented in Table 6.

Table 6. Validity of measuring instrument.

Construct	Scale Items	Factor Loading	Cronbach's Alpha	CR	AVE	MSV
Information Value (INF)	The information shared by the AI influencer is useful.	0.795	0.838	0.840	0.635	0.494
	The information shared by the AI influencer is helpful to find product information.	0.809				
	The information shared by the AI influencer is important for selecting the product.	0.788				
Entertainment Value (ENT)	The AI influencer's posts are entertaining.	0.825	0.876	0.877	0.704	0.494
	Watching AI influencer's posts is fun.	0.855				
	Watching AI influencer's posts is thrilling.	0.837				
Attractiveness (ATT)	The AI influencer is attractive.	0.829	0.856	0.875	0.700	0.614
	The AI influencer is charismatic.	0.792				
	The AI influencer is good-looking.	0.885				
Human-likeness (HL)	The AI influencer looks like a human.	0.804	0.849	0.838	0.635	0.614
	The AI influencer is life-like.	0.748				
	The AI influencer has human-like expressions.	0.807				
Credibility (CRE)	The AI influencer(s) is/are trustworthy.	0.807	0.854	0.770	0.540	0.537
	The AI influencer(s) is/are reliable.	0.912				
	The virtual influencers are experts in their field.	0.731				
Customer Engagement (CE)	I watch the pictures/photos and videos posted on the virtual influencer's social media page.	0.767	0.794	0.839	0.635	0.537
	I like the content posted on the virtual influencer's social media page.	0.840				
	I follow the virtual influencer's social media page.	0.787				
Purchase Intention (PI)	I will buy products promoted by the AI influencer in the near future.	0.791	0.869	0.870	0.626	0.527
	I intend to purchase the products promoted by the AI influencer in the near future	0.790				
	It is likely that I will purchase the products promoted by the AI influencer in the near future.	0.730				
	I expect to purchase the products promoted by the AI influencer in the near future.	0.850				

Discriminant validity helps to check how the constructs are empirically different from one another. It helps to evaluate the degree of difference between overlaying constructs [87]. The assessment of discriminant validity was checked by the criteria fixed by Fornell and Larcker [89]. They recommend that the square root of the average variance extracted

(AVE) needs to be more than the corresponding correlations between the construct and the residual of other constructs [90]. On the diagonal, the AVE value was placed to evaluate them against other factors in the correlation coefficient. The findings revealed values exceeding 0.5, validating the discriminant nature of all the factors, and details are presented in Table 7.

Table 7. Discriminant validity.

	INF	ENT	ATT	HL	CRE	CE	PI
INF	0.797						
ENT	0.703	0.839					
ATT	0.233	0.160	0.836				
HL	0.167	0.049	0.784	0.797			
CRE	0.683	0.508	0.312	0.252	0.735		
CE	0.679	0.608	0.448	0.400	0.733	0.797	
PI	0.574	0.315	0.395	0.435	0.709	0.726	0.791

5.4. Evaluating the Structural Model

The analysis shows that the measurement model of the proposed conceptual model was found to be reliable and valid. The next step is to measure the inner structural model outcomes and to evaluate the fit of the structural equation model. The measurement results should meet the standard requirements of the model fit index. The critical ration (C.R.) value should exceed 1.96, and the direction of the path coefficient should align with the assumed direction in previous research. The model fit index is presented in Table 8, and the threshold values are based on Hu and Bentler [91]’s recommendations. The model fit for the proposed model was evaluated using the standardized root mean square residual (SRMR), the normed fit index (NFI), the comparative fit index (CFI), the root mean square error of approximation (RMSEA) and the goodness of fit index (GFI). The GFI is an important measure to check the model fit and its value needs to be close to 1. The analysis shows all the model fit indexes were found to be in the acceptable range, so further analysis could be conducted.

Table 8. Measurement results of model fit index.

Name of Index	Model Fit of Research Model	Threshold Values	Interpretation
CMIN/DF	2.550	<3.00	Excellent
NFI	0.926	>0.90	Excellent
CFI	0.947	>0.95	Acceptable
GFI	0.910	>0.90	Excellent
SRMR	0.052	<0.08	Excellent
RMSEA	0.061	<0.06	Acceptable
PClose	0.040	>0.05	Acceptable

Note: threshold values are based on Hu and Bentler [91]’s cutoff criteria for fit indexes.

5.5. Hypothesis Testing

All the eleven proposed hypotheses were tested using the IBM AMOS version 29 software. The results of the analysis are presented in Table 9. The results show that Hypotheses 1 and 2 are related to the informative value of AI influencers’ generated content, positively impacting engagement and purchase intention. Hypotheses 9 and 10 are related to credibility, which is found to positively impact engagement and purchase intention. Credibility was found to be the most significant factor influencing engagement with $\beta = 0.600$, and purchase intention with $\beta = 0.554$. Hypotheses 5 and 6 are related to attrac-

tiveness and the human-likeness of the AI influencer, while attractiveness is not associated with purchase intention as the p value is greater than the acceptable level of 0.05. Interestingly, the entertainment value (Hypotheses 3 and 4) shows a negative association with purchase intention but a positive association with consumer engagement. Hypothesis 11 is related to consumer engagement and purchase intention, and the result shows it positively impacts purchase intention.

Table 9. Path coefficients of estimate model.

Hypothesis	Path	Std. β	Std. Error	t-Statistics	p Values	Results
H ₁	INF → CE	0.216	0.040	5.360	0.001	Accepted
H ₃	ENT → CE	0.252	0.039	6.388	0.001	Accepted
H ₅	ATT → CE	0.106	0.039	2.695	0.007	Accepted
H ₇	HL → CE	0.149	0.038	3.954	0.001	Accepted
H ₉	CRE → CE	0.600	0.086	6.990	0.001	Accepted
H ₁₁	CE → PI	0.496	0.104	4.774	0.001	Accepted
H ₂	INF → PI	0.206	0.049	4.164	0.001	Accepted
H ₄	ENT → PI	−0.223	0.050	−4.483	0.001	Accepted
H ₆	ATT → PI	−0.023	0.033	−0.695	0.487	Not Accepted
H ₈	HL → PI	0.188	0.046	4.100	0.001	Accepted
H ₁₀	CRE → PI	0.554	0.107	5.164	0.001	Accepted

sig $p < 0.05$.

5.6. The Mediating Effect of Consumer Engagement

This study employed the Hayes Model to test whether consumer engagement mediates the relationship between informative value, entertainment value, attractiveness, human-likeness, credibility and purchase intention. The AMOS software was used to estimate the direct and indirect effects of the five variables, with consumer engagement as the mediator, in order to understand the mediation effect on purchase intention. The mediating effect is checked by conducting bootstrapping as well as bias-corrected percentile bootstrapping, with 2000 resamples to construct 95% confidence intervals for the indirect effects. The confidence interval bounds are used to check whether the indirect effects are statistically significant, based on the criteria proposed by Preacher and Hayes [92]. The outcome of the analysis is presented in Table 10.

The results showed a significant effect of informative value ($\beta = 0.206$, $t = 4.164$, $p < 0.001$), entertainment value ($\beta = -0.223$, $t = -4.483$, $p < 0.001$), human-likeness ($\beta = 0.188$, $t = 4.100$, $p < 0.001$) and credibility ($\beta = -0.554$, $t = -5.164$, $p < 0.001$) on purchase intention. The attractiveness shows no significant effect on purchase intention (Refer Table 9). The Hayes process with 2000 bootstrapping samples was used to test the single mediation test. The analysis results presented in Table 10 and Figure 2 show that the informative value (H_{11a}), human-likeness (H_{11d}) and credibility (H_{11e}) were partially mediated by consumer engagement. Attractiveness (H_{11b}) shows no direct effect on purchase intention but shows an indirect effect through engagement. Inconsistent mediation models are models where at least one mediated effect has a different sign from other mediated or direct effects in a model [85]. Entertainment value (H_{11c}) has a negative effect on purchase intention but shows a positive effect when it is mediated through consumer engagement. This is considered an inconsistent mediation model, and the negative effect of the entertainment value is higher towards purchase intention. This result reveals that the attractiveness and entertainment value of AI influencers shows that it is useful for improving consumer engagement but least effective on purchase intention.

Table 10. Bootstrap analysis of mediation effects.

	Point Estimate	Std. Error	Bias-Corrected 95% CI		p Value
			Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Indirect effects					
INF → CE → PI	0.107	0.042	0.048	0.182	0.002
ENT → CE → PI	0.125	0.044	0.063	0.205	0.001
ATT → CE → PI	0.053	0.032	0.011	0.112	0.012
HL → CE → PI	0.074	0.040	0.014	0.147	0.047
CRE → CE → PI	0.297	0.110	0.165	0.516	0.001
Direct effects					
INF → PI	0.205	0.078	0.080	0.337	0.004
ENT → PI	-0.223	0.069	-0.329	-0.109	0.003
ATT → PI	-0.023	0.050	-0.105	0.062	0.509
HL → PI	0.188	0.071	0.070	0.296	0.019
CRE → PI	0.554	0.143	0.334	0.816	0.001
Total effects					
INF → CE → PI	0.313	0.072	0.202	0.435	0.001
ENT → CE → PI	-0.098	0.066	-0.207	0.010	0.140
ATT → CE → PI	0.029	0.056	-0.049	0.131	0.573
HL → CE → PI	0.262	0.075	0.142	0.383	0.002
CRE → CE → PI	0.851	0.139	0.672	1.122	0.001

Figure 2. Final model.

6. Discussion

6.1. General Discussion of Results

This study focused on testing AI influencers’ informative value, entertainment value, attractiveness, human-likeness and credibility effects the on consumer engagement and purchase intention. The research used SEM to identify the factors that influence a consumer’s engagement and intention to purchase brands promoted by an AI Influencer. The

results of the empirical analysis have shown some important findings, which are discussed in this section. The five independent variables (informative value, entertainment value, attractiveness, human-likeness and credibility) significantly contribute to explaining consumer engagement, but entertainment value and attractiveness were not found to influence purchase intention.

Hypotheses 1 and 2 were related to informative value, which is accepted as the p -value was less than 0.05, which means that the informative value of influencers' posts has a positive effect ($\beta = 0.216$) on consumer engagement on their social media page and has a positive effect on purchase intention, which is supported by previous research findings [46,70]. The mediating effect analysis shows that they are partially mediated by consumer engagement. This relationship shows that consumers are more interested in watching informative content posts by virtual influencers, which affects purchase intention. Hypotheses 3 and 4 are related to entertainment value which is accepted as the p -value was less than 0.05, which means that the entertainment value of influencers' posts has a positive effect ($\beta = 0.252$) on consumer engagement on their social media page and has a positive effect on purchase intention ($\beta = -0.223$). The effectiveness of social media content in generating customer brand engagement depends on its ability to be entertaining, which is supported by previous research findings [93]. Interestingly, the entertainment value was found to negatively affect the purchase intention but exhibit a positive association with consumer engagement. The mediating effect analysis shows that they are partially mediated by consumer engagement. This relationship shows that consumers prefer to engage with virtual influencers posting with entertainment content, but it does not contribute to influencing the consumer to purchase. But the research findings show there is no direct effect on purchase intention, which is also supported by the previous research findings of Liu and Zhen [46].

Hypothesis 5 is accepted as the p -value was less than 0.05, which means that the attractiveness of AI influencers has a positive effect ($\beta = 0.105$) on consumer engagement on their social media page. Hypothesis 6 is not accepted as the p -value was higher than 0.05. The findings of our research show that AI influencers' attractiveness was not directly associated with purchase intention but was indirectly affected through consumer engagement. This shows that AI attractiveness is required to attract the followers to engage, but it may not significantly contribute to purchase intention directly. This matches with previous studies conducted on virtual influencers [61]. Many scholars in the advertisement literature have analyzed the effect of endorsers' attractiveness on purchase intention. Applying the source attractiveness model [60], the current research finding shows that the attractiveness of AI influencers (Hypothesis 6) was found to have no direct effect on purchase intention but exhibited an indirect effect through consumer engagement on the social media pages. This relationship shows that consumers prefer to engage with attractive virtual influencers. This was supported by Rakovic [94]'s research findings on perceived attractiveness and para-social interaction.

Hypotheses 7 and 8 are accepted as p -value was less than 0.05, which means that the human-likeness of VIs has a positive effect ($\beta = 0.152$) on consumer engagement on their social media page. This relationship shows that consumers prefer to engage with virtual influencers who look like humans. This is also supported by the previous research findings of Xie-Carson et al. (2023) [19] on user engagement with virtual influencers in tourism contexts. The human-likeness was also found to be partially mediated by consumer engagement to improve purchase intention. Hypotheses 9 and 10 were accepted as the p -value was less than 0.05, which means that the credibility of AI influencers has a positive effect ($\beta = 0.600$) on consumer engagement on their social media pages and exhibits a positive effect on purchase intention ($\beta = 0.554$). This relationship shows that

consumers prefer to engage with virtual influencers posting with credible content. The current research shows the perceived credibility of the influencer is one of the most important factors for purchase intention, which is also supported by the previous research findings of Magano et al. on virtual influencers [78].

For Hypothesis 11, which tested the relationship between consumer engagement and purchase intention, the results showed a strong association as the p -value was less than 0.05. The analysis results presented in Table 10 reveal the mediating effect of consumer engagement on purchase intention. The informative value (H_{11a}), human-likeness (H_{11d}) and credibility (H_{11e}) were partially mediated by consumer engagement. Attractiveness (H_{11b}) showed no direct effect on purchase intention but showed an indirect effect through engagement. Entertainment value (H_{11c}) had a negative effect on purchase intention but showed positive effect when it was mediated through consumer engagement. The engagement and purchase intention association match with previous research work on virtual influencers (e.g., Wolff [95]). This finding reveals that brands can increase their brand sales by launching AI influencer marketing on their social media pages. It is necessary for the brands to build the credibility of the AI influencers to influence their followers to purchase their brands. Consumer engagement is an important factor for attracting the brand followers to their social media pages. The consumer engagement improves the followers' purchase intentions.

6.2. Theoretical Contribution

The current study makes several significant contributions to the influencer marketing literature, specifically AI-based virtual influencers, by using Uncanny Valley Theory and Anthropomorphism Theory [31,32], the Advertising Value Model [33], Source Credibility Theory [34], Uses and Gratifications Theory (UGT) [35] and the Computer as Social Actors Paradigm (CASA) [36]. This study addresses inconsistencies and gaps in understanding the AI influencers' effect on consumer engagement and purchase intention. First, this study extends the application of the uncanny valley theory and anthropomorphism theory on AI-based influencers. This research's findings show that AI influencers' human-likeness improves consumer engagement, and these interactions positively impact purchase intentions. This research's findings match with the previous research work of Gerlick (2023) [42]. This research contributes to the virtual influencers literature as the findings contradict the negative perception towards virtual influencers (e.g., Franke et al. [14] and Sands et al. [11]). The AI influencer Naina's campaign was able to create a positive response from the respondents as it exhibits a strong sense of identification among the young audience, perceived uniqueness, and it interacts with other virtual characters and not humans.

This study makes important contributions to the source attractiveness model literature by emphasizing the effect of attractiveness of AI influencers on purchase intention. The findings of our research show that AI influencers' attractiveness was not directly associated with purchase intention, but indirectly affected consumer engagement. This matches with previous studies conducted on virtual influencers [61]. The study attempts to develop an integrated model demonstrating how an AI influencer can impact the purchase intention. The credibility of the AI influencers was found to be the most important factor to influence engagement and purchase intention. This finding makes an important contribution to source credibility theory by extending its application to AI-based virtual influencers. The study confirms that the informative and entertainment value of the influencers' posted content influence engagement on the social media pages. This study reveals the mediating role of engagement on social media pages and consumer purchase intentions, and the findings show that all five variables were partially mediated by consumer engagement. The

findings contribute to a better understanding of the AI-based virtual influencers' influences on consumer engagement and purchase intentions.

6.3. Managerial Contribution

Marketing managers are interested in implementing AI influencers for their brand promotions but are still uncertain about how successfully consumers will engage with them on their social media pages [96]. The results of this study offer valuable insights for digital marketers aiming to utilize AI technology to improve consumer engagement and increase purchase intentions. The main factors which contribute to increasing consumer engagement and purchase intentions is credibility. Credibility helps to build trust and loyalty with an audience, which is essential for increasing brand engagement. It is necessary to provide honest content about the product to enhance credibility. Based on Qu and Baek [97]'s research findings, trust towards AI influencers improves if the campaign is created in a virtual environment interacting with virtual characters.

The research findings suggests that the attractiveness and entertainment value of AI influencers can help with creating engagement but does not directly contribute to improving purchase intention. This study assists managers with understanding the role of AI influencers in recommending brands. As these AI influencers are widely used on social media, it is necessary for the brands to increase engagement. The entertainment value of the post and attractiveness significantly increase the followers' engagement on the social media pages of AI influencers. The marketers also need to post informative content and build credibility to improve the purchase intention. The consistent posting of high-quality useful content which provides valuable information to their audience will enhance the credibility of the AI influencer. It is necessary for the managers to build trust with their followers by sharing user experiences and opinions that resonate with the audience. The trust can also be improved by responding to comments.

7. Conclusions and Research Limitations

In conclusion, while this study makes important contributions, it also sets the direction for future work on AI influences in the emerging market and in AI-driven digital transformation. This research aims to address the gaps in the literature about AI influencers' marketing. Of the eleven hypotheses checked, ten are empirically validated. From the analysis, perceived credibility is found to be the most important variable for consumer engagement and purchase intention. Attractiveness and entertainment value were found to have an indirect effect on purchase intention through consumer engagement. The research result advocates brands to adopt strong and engaging AI influencers' presence on social media platforms like Instagram for increasing their engagement and purchase intention.

This research investigates the effect of AI influencers on consumers' engagement and intention to purchase within the context of Instagram. However, future research might examine consumers' engagement with various other social media platforms. This study did not focus on any specific product category, and future research can study the consumers' response to posts related to a specific product. This research is based on a quantitative research method in the form of a questionnaire to collect the necessary data. Future research could consider using a mixed method approach as this would provide additional information with respect to the role of the AI-based virtual influencer. By generalizing the results, future research could include participants from different countries. Future research could adopt various types of AI influencer based on its characteristics like gender, age and skin color.

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